

CLASSIFYING ADULT CONTENT USING NAÏVE BAYES

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Abstract

In today’s World Wide Web any kind of content is always at everyone’s fingertip. But not every content meets ethical, cultural or legal norms. In particular, regular use of online pornography is associated with sexually aggressive behaviour. Since web search engines are pivotal as an entry point to the web, they need to address this issue. This article presents a naïve Bayes classifier for detecting adult web sites in context of a web crawler. The classifier is solely based on textual content of home pages. The approach is fast and easy to implement and experiments show high accuracy.

INTRODUCTION

Since frequent use of violent pornography by adolescent is suspected to increase sexually coercive and aggressive behavior [1], it appears ethically indicated to filter adult content. Moreover, ignoring cultural or legal norms pose reputational and financial risk to search engine owners.

Many reported filtering techniques try to detect adult media content, others are based on textual content and some use a combination of techniques, see [2] for a more thorough discussion. The presented naïve Bayes classifier, trained on the text of home pages, allows a web crawler to apply a simple and effective strategy: Whenever an unseen domain is met, we first fetch the home page for classification.

NAÏVE BAYES CLASSIFICATION

Following [3] a *multinomial naïve Bayes* classifier estimates the class $\hat{c}(d)$ of a document $d = (w_i)_{i=1}^n$ (“bag-of-words” representation) by maximizing the posterior $P(c|d)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{c}(d) &= \arg \max_{c \in C} P(c|d) = \arg \max_{c \in C} \frac{P(c)P(d|c)}{P(d)} \\ &= \arg \max_{c \in C} P(c) \prod_{i=1}^n P(w_i|c) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The prior $P(c)$ and conditional probabilities $P(w_i|c)$ are estimated as relative frequencies:

$$P(c) = \frac{N_c}{N}, \quad P(w_i|c) = \frac{f(w_i,c) + 1}{\sum_{w \in V} (f(w,c) + 1)},$$

where N_c , N is the number of documents in c resp. in total and $f(w_i,c)$, $f(w,c)$ denote token counts in class c . Note the Laplace-smoothing ‘+1’ to avoid zeros in equation (1).

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Training data consists of 217 adult and 4351 non-adult home pages. For each retrieved home page all HTML tags were removed and the remaining text added to the vocabulary. Words that occurred only once or in more than 50% of

randomly split into ten folds for cross-validation. Each validation run builds a vocabulary from the nine training folds and classifies the pages in the test fold using equation (1).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results in Tab. 1 show a high accuracy of $\frac{210+4322}{4568} = 99.2\%$. Note that the precision depends on the ratio of adult and non-adult pages in the training set, as shown in Fig. 1. Bearing this in mind, our results are very competitive with results from Largillier et al. [2], who report an accuracy of 97.2% (precision 98.3%) for 839 adult and 314 “safe” pages.

		true values		precision
		adult	¬adult	
out	adult	210	29	$\frac{210}{210+29} = 87.9\%$
	¬adult	7	4322	$\frac{4322}{4322+7} = 99.8\%$
recall		$\frac{210}{210+7} = 96.8\%$	$\frac{4322}{4322+29} = 99.3\%$	

Table 1: Confusion matrix for 10-fold cross-validation including derived micro-average precision and recall.

Figure 1: Precision versus ratio of classes in training set.

CONCLUSION

To further improve accuracy and especially the unwanted misclassification of non-adult pages as adult pages, a number of improvements could be explored in future work. One straightforward extension that comes to mind, is not only to analyse home pages, but additionally a fixed number of linked pages for each domain.

REFERENCES

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the pages were removed. The remaining 4568 pages were